

Why Wikipedia must consider inclusion of scientific hypotheses

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#gasocrine

I have recently proposed several new terms in biology, all of which have been published in peer-reviewed journals. The new terms I have proposed include gasoreceptor, aquareceptor, riboceptor, gasocrine signaling, and thermocrine signaling. However, these terms do not yet have dedicated Wikipedia pages or are not included in existing Wikipedia pages. For example, riboceptors represent a fundamental hypothesis that can help us understand the origin of life and the origin of cellular and interorganism communication during evolution and the RNA world. However, this concept does not pass Wikipedia's strict rules and regulations. If these scientific terms and concepts are considered speculative and cannot be added to Wikipedia, then why is there a Wikipedia page about God? Has God's existence been experimentally proven? What proof do we have that God is no different from, say, the concept of synchronicity? As many students around the world lack access to education and may turn to Wikipedia for free self-education, while misinformation must not be spread through Wikipedia, we as scientists must consider what should be done to add the latest scientific theories and hypotheses to Wikipedia. At a time when we are facing significant challenges such as climate change and global warming, the sooner students are exposed to the latest concepts, the sooner we may find solutions not only from Ivy League institutions, but also from the corners of the world, as in the case of Srinivasa Ramanujan in the past.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

None.

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